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References

1. Y. A. WALI and Y. M. HASSAN., *Proc. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.*, 1965, **87**, 264.
2. B. S. LULLA and D.S. JOHAR., *Current Sci.*, 1955, **24**, 92.
3. H. WYMAN and J. K. PALMER., *Plant Physiology*, 1964, **39**, 630.
4. S.M. PATRIDGE., *Biochem. J.*, 1948, **42**, 238.
5. K. H. SLOTTA and J. PRIMOSIGH. *Nature*, 1951, **168**, 696.
6. S. M. PARTRIDGE, *Nature*, 1943, **164**, 443.
7. C. S. MARVEL and R. D. RANDS, (Jr.) *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2642.
8. M. MAKI and Y. SATO., *Kaseigaku-Zasshi*, 1959, **20**, 406.
9. G. L. POLAND, H. W. VON LOESECKE, M. W. BRENNER., J. T. MANION and P. L. HARRIS, *Food Res.*, 1937, **2**, 403.
10. EDWARD ROSS and C. L. MILLER., *Food Sci.*, 1963, **28**, 193.
11. B. S. LULLA and D.S. JOHAR, *Current Sci.*, 1954, **23**, 362.

When anthranilic acid was used as substrate, the primary amino group is preferentially phenylated to that of -COOH group, hence accounting for our obtaining N-phenylanthranilic acid. However, increase in reaction time at elevated temperatures afforded N, N-diphenyl phenyl anthranilate, i. e., -NH₂ and -COOH groups were fully phenylated. But in any case it was not possible to isolate N, N-diphenylanthranilic acid, N-phenyl-phenylanthranilate or phenylanthranilate.

Our careful and repeated experiment with salicylic acid yielded only phenyl salicylate and formation of *o*-phenoxybenzoic acid or *o*-phenoxy phenylbenzoate was not observed at all.

The yields are reported only of benzoates or maximum phenylated final products.

The results are summarised in the following table :

Reaction of Benzyne with Carboxylic Acids

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GENERAL survey of literature reveals that little work has been done on the reactions of benzyne with carboxylic acids¹⁻⁸. We, therefore, studied the reactions of benzyne with chlorobenzoic acids,

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References

1. M. STILES, R. G. MILLER and U. BURCKHARDT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1792.
2. R. HOWE, *J. Chem. Soc.(C)*, 1966, 478.
3. S. F. SYKE, A. R. MARSHALL and J. P. WATSON, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, **22**, 2515.
4. E. MCNELIS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 3188.

Sl. No.	Substrate	Product†	m.p. (°C)*	Yield (%) Procedure	
				(a)	(b)
1.	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	Phenyl- <i>o</i> -chlorobenzoate	36-37	22	34
2.	<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	Phenyl- <i>m</i> -chlorobenzoate	52-53	22	33
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	Phenyl- <i>p</i> -chlorobenzoate	100	27	44
4.	Phenoxyacetic acid	Phenyl-phenoxy acetate	54-56	24	32
5.	Salicylic acid	Phenyl salicylate	41-43	28	47
6.	Anthranilic acid	N,N-Diphenyl-phenyl-anthranilate	83-84	9	-

* All the m.p.'s are uncorrected.

† Characterisation of products was done by m.p., m.m.p., Co-TLC and ir spectra comparison with that of authentic sample.

phenoxyacetic acid etc. The reactions were carried out in dry THF and procedures⁹ (a) and (b) were followed for the generation of benzyne. When benzene was used as reaction medium in place of THF biphenyl was obtained besides corresponding benzoate. However, when procedure¹⁰ (b) was followed acridone was inevitable product irrespective of the solvent used.

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5. P. SARTORI and M. WEIDENBRUCH, *Angew. Chem.*, 1965, **77**, 1076 ; *Angew.Chem. Internat. Ed.* 1965, **4**, 1072.
6. H. E. SIMMONS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 691.
7. G. KOBRICH, *Chem. Ber.*, 1963, **96**, 2544.
8. R. W. HOFFMANN, "Dehydrobenzene and Cycloalkynes", Academic Press, New York, 1966.
9. M. STILES and R. G. MILLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1960, **82**, 3802.
10. L. FRIEDMAN and F. M. LOGULLO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1549.